

COMPUTATIONAL MODELLING OF INCIDENT SOLAR RADIATION AND APPLICATION FOR THERMAL LOADS CALCULATION IN BUILDINGS

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Abstract *Solar radiation is a significant factor in the heat gains of buildings, directly affecting indoor comfort and increasing the demand for air conditioning systems, and consequently, energy consumption. The present work aims at computationally modelling incident solar radiation, allowing its integration into the calculation of thermal loads in buildings. The adopted methodology considers three main components: the sun position, the radiation intensity and the characteristics of the surfaces exposed to this radiation. The sun position is determined based on latitude, longitude, date, and local time. Radiation intensity is estimated according to the sun position on a given day and time of analysis. The radiation model was developed and implemented in Python and validated by comparing its results with those of a commercial reference program. The results showed differences of less than 0.1% in the maximum annual analysis and a maximum deviation of 4.9% during hours of increased irradiance variation. The annual analysis, considering a building located in Lisbon, revealed that the maximum irradiance on North-facing surface occurred in June (219 W/m²), while the maximum for the East and West surfaces was verified in April (812 W/m²). The maximum irradiance on the South-facing surface was observed in January (913 W/m²). The hourly analysis on the day of maximum thermal load showed that the highest irradiance was verified on the East-facing surface (747.8 W/m² at 8 a.m.), followed by West-facing surface (744.7 W/m² at 4 p.m.) and the South-facing surface (734.5 W/m² at 12 p.m.), with the lowest irradiance observed on the North-facing surface (117.9 W/m²). The model was evaluated for various locations, demonstrating that latitude variation influence both the maximum irradiance and the duration of solar exposure, with these factors depending on the specific period of the year. The variation in longitude resulted in a time shift in the irradiance profile throughout the day.*

1. INTRODUCTION

Thermal loads in buildings refer to the heat exchange between the indoor and outdoor environments, leading to variations in indoor temperature and humidity. These variations can significantly impact indoor environmental conditions, potentially requiring the implementation of air conditioning systems to ensure thermal comfort. The thermal loads of a building originate from both external and internal sources. External thermal loads are influenced by climatic conditions and the thermal properties of the building envelope, including walls, roofs, windows, among others. Internal thermal loads, on the other hand, are the result from activities within the building and are primarily associated with occupancy, equipment and artificial lighting. The heat transfer by conduction and convection is highly dependent on climatic conditions, particularly external temperature. When an indoor space is directly exposed to the exterior, radiative heat transfer must also be considered, taking into account incident solar radiation on external elements such as external walls, roof and windows.

Solar radiation is defined as the energy emitted by the sun in the form of electromagnetic waves. This radiation constitutes a mode of heat transfer that occurs whenever a body has a temperature above absolute zero (0 K). Unlike other heat transfer mechanisms, such as conduction or convection, energy transfer via electromagnetic waves does not require the presence of a material medium.

In the study shown by An et al., (2020) [1], methods used in building energy modelling programs for direct incident solar radiation calculations are first analysed and an improved method is proposed. The algorithm assumes that the solar irradiance changes linearly within a 1-h period and can be estimated based on the solar irradiance at the half clock and slope. The collected direct normal solar irradiance data from various stations in China were used to evaluate the performance of proposed method and compare the results with those from three conventional methods used in building energy modelling programs. The results of the estimated direct incident solar radiation show that the proposed method achieves the best accuracy, followed by the methods used in DOE 2, EnergyPlus, and DeST. The proposed method obtains more accurate results when using the middle point of every timestep and by applying a shorter timestep, which can be adopted in current building energy modelling programs to improve the accuracy of a simulated building performance and photovoltaic energy production.

A new methodology of calculation of the direct, diffuse and reflected incident solar radiation, was developed in all type of surfaces [2]. This methodology is applicable in problems related to solar access (space heating in buildings, shadowing of open spaces), solar gains (space cooling in buildings), and daylighting. The proposed methodology is based on a method of characterization that can take into account the surfaces that can block or reflect the solar radiation toward the building. The proposed methodology contemplates the complete process, beginning with how to characterize surfaces and volumes, and finishing with the calculation of all the components of the incident solar radiation on an external surface. The quantitative characterization of the phenomenon has been carried out on a real case, and a new concept has

been defined: the modified albedo. With the help of this parameter, it has been possible to compare the solution given by a simplified model, and the one obtained from the proposed methodology.

The main contribution of the research presented by Marino et al., (2018) [3] is the development of a new methodology to obtain the external surface temperature of walls, considering diurnal variations of the external environment temperature. The theoretical calculation of the surface temperature requires knowing the evolution of the air external temperature, the total incident solar radiation on the wall and the external surface thermal resistance of the air boundary layer. The effect of solar radiation on the heat transfer through the building envelope can be considered, while the parameters related to the sol-air temperature calculation can be experimentally validated at the construction's specific location. The results were compared to measurements performed applying Infrared thermography. The results improve the understanding of the dynamic response of the different layers that compose the wall and the contribution of these layers to the global thermal behaviour of the wall.

An approach for predicting global radiation on any window plane has been presented [4]. Optical and thermal properties of window glazing system have been analysed to evaluate the glazing performance in increasing the inside temperature due to the incidence of global radiation. The thermal model considers laminar heat transfer for natural and forced convection process according to the ambient conditions. A mathematical model simulating the glazing temperature due to global radiation and hence the solar heat gain of building interior through window has been developed. The simulated glazing temperatures with the corresponding window plane global radiation were validated by experimental values. The estimated error between simulated and experimental values of window plane radiation and the corresponding glazing temperature are obtained below 5%. Thus, the radiation and thermal simulation models may be used for predicting the thermal performance of building due to solar radiation.

Demain et al., (2023) [5] presented a study that evaluates the performance of various models transposing solar radiation from horizontal to inclined surface. This study is relevant since global and diffuse solar radiation intensities are, in general, measured on horizontal surfaces, whereas stationary solar conversion systems (both flat plate solar collector and solar photovoltaic) are mounted on inclined surface to maximize the amount of solar radiation incident on the collector surface. Solar radiation data measured in Uccle, Belgium were used for validation purposes. Individual model performance is assessed between the calculated and measured solar global radiation on a south-oriented tilted surface using statistical methods. Since statistical validation procedures revealed that none of the considered model performs well under all types of sky conditions, a new model, resulting from the coupling of three models acting under different sky conditions, was developed for Belgium. The ability of the coupled model to handle hourly and daily data is discussed, concluding that best results are obtained for hourly data.

An update status of research and applications of various methods was shown for determining solar panel tilt angle using various optimization techniques [6]. Determining the optimum tilt

angle allows for maximum incident solar radiation, resulting in optimum sizing of solar systems. This paper describes solar radiation modelling on sloped surfaces, defining solar time, solar geometry and radiation distribution. Solar radiation on sloped surfaces can be defined considering Isotropic model or Anisotropic model. The optimum tilt angles are determined by changing tilt angle from 0° to 90° in different steps and using optimization techniques such as Genetic Algorithm, Simulated Annealing and Artificial Neural Network. For better accuracy of optimum tilt angle calculations different anisotropic models and optimization techniques can be tested at different sites. The study shows that for maximum energy gain, the optimum tilt angle for solar systems must be determined accurately for each location.

This article aims to implement a computational model for incident solar radiation, enabling its integration into thermal loads calculation for buildings. The adopted methodology is based on three main components: the solar position, the intensity of incident radiation and the characteristics of the surfaces exposed to this radiation.

2. THERMAL LOADS CALCULATION

Thermal loads can be calculated by computational models that include the building characteristics and the various heat transfer modes. ASHRAE [7] presents the computational methods such as the Transfer Function, the Cooling Load Temperature Difference method and Total Equivalent Temperature Difference/Time Averaging method. More recent editions of the ASHRAE Handbook [8] present the Heat Balance Method and the Radiant Time Series Method as refined approaches for calculating thermal loads, with a particular focus on accurately incorporating solar radiation effects.

The present study evaluates a computational application for thermal load calculation, as detailed in Agostinho, et al. (2024) [9]. This application implements the Transfer Function Method to estimate the thermal loads of a building while utilising external temperature and solar radiation data sourced from other programs. According to the Transfer Function Method, heat gain through external walls and roofs is determined by equation 1 [7]. This heat gain is dependent on the surface area of the analysed wall or roof, the indoor air temperature and the conduction transfer function coefficients. The conduction transfer function allows the modelling of conduction heat transfer through the wall. Additionally, the heat gain in external walls and roofs also is affected by the sol-air temperature, which accounts for the influence of solar radiation and outdoor conditions.

$$q_{e,\theta} = A \cdot \left[\sum_{n=0} b_n(t_{sol,\theta-n}) - \sum_{n=1} d_n \left(\frac{q_{e,\theta-n}}{A} \right) - t_{in} \sum_{n=0} c_n \right] \quad (1)$$

where:

- $q_{e,\theta}$ – heat gain through wall or roof, at calculation hour θ [W];
- A – surface area [m²];
- $t_{sol,\theta-n}$ – sol-air temperature at hour $\theta-n$ [°C];
- t_{in} – indoor air temperature [°C];
- b_n, c_n e d_n – conduction transfer function coefficients [-].

The sol-air temperature is the outdoor air temperature that, in the absence of all radiation sources, results in the same heat flux into a surface as would the combined effect of incident solar radiation and convective heat exchange with the outdoor air. Thus, it is the equivalent of temperature considering the outdoor air temperature and the influence of solar radiation.

Heat gain through windows is obtained from the combination of two forms of heat transfer: conduction and radiation. The conductive heat gain of windows depends on the overall heat transfer coefficient (U-value), the surface area and outdoor and indoor air temperature, as shown in equation 2 [7].

$$q_{w,c} = U \cdot A \cdot (t_{out} - t_{in}) \quad (2)$$

where:

- $q_{w,c}$ – conduction heat gain through window [W];
- U – overall heat transfer coefficient [W/(m²·K)]
- A – surface area [m²];
- t_{out} – outdoor air temperature [°C];
- t_{in} – indoor air temperature [°C].

The radiation heat gain through windows is determined as shown in equation 3 [7]:

$$q_{w,r} = A \cdot SHGF \cdot SC \quad (3)$$

where:

- $q_{w,r}$ – radiation heat gain through window [W];
- A – surface area [m²];
- $SHGF$ – solar heat gain factor [W/m²];
- SC – shading coefficient [-].

The shading coefficient (SC) is a characteristic of a window that quantifies the amount of incoming solar energy in relation to a reference window. This coefficient can either be provided by the manufacturer or calculated based on the composition of the glazing system, considering the number of glass layers and their characteristics. The solar heat gain factor (SHGF) represents the fraction of incident solar irradiance that crosses the glazing and contributes to the heat gain inside the space. This includes both the directly transmitted component of irradiance and the portion that is absorbed by the glazing and subsequently re-emitted as heat.

In summary, solar radiation influences the thermal loads of buildings through external envelope elements, such as external walls roofs and windows. The impact of solar radiation is accounted for using sol-air temperature for external walls and roofs, and the solar heat gain factor for windows. Both parameters depend on the intensity of incident solar irradiance on the respective surface.

3. METHODOLOGY

3.1. CALCULATION OF SOLAR RADIATION

The solar radiation follows a sequence of three main variables: 1) solar time; 2) solar position and 3) solar irradiance. Solar time is estimated from the apparent angular motion of the sun, considering that noon is the moment when the sun passes in the local meridian. The solar time is calculated from the local time by equation 4 [10].

$$h_{solar} = h_{local} + (ET + 4 \cdot (l_{st} - l_{local})) \cdot \frac{1}{60} \quad (4)$$

where:

- h_{solar} – solar time [h];
- h_{local} – local time [h];
- ET – equation of time [min];
- l_{st} – local standard time meridian [°];
- l_{local} – local longitude [°].

The equation of time (ET) establishes the relationship between the mean solar time and apparent solar time, accounting for seasonal variations. This value fluctuates throughout the year and can be obtained from tables, such as those provided by ASHRAE [7], or calculated using specific equations, as presented in Goswami (2015) [10]. The local longitude corresponds to the geographical longitude of the building under analysis. On the other hand, the local standard time meridian represents the central longitude of a given time zone, determined by multiplying the time difference from Greenwich Mean Time (GMT) by 15 degrees per hour.

Once the solar time is determined, the sun position can be characterised by two fundamental angular parameters, as illustrated in Figure 1: solar altitude and solar azimuth.

Figure 1. Position of the sun, its path and defining angles

Solar altitude is the angle between the sun's rays and the horizontal plane, which can be obtained using equation 5 [7].

$$\sin Alt_{sl} = \cos Lat \cdot \cos \delta_{solar} \cdot \cos h_{ang} + \sin Lat \cdot \sin \delta_{solar} \quad (5)$$

where:

- Alt_{sl} – solar altitude [°];
- Lat – latitude [°];
- δ_{solar} – solar declination [°];
- hang – solar hour angle [°].

The angle of solar hour describes the sun position relative to the local meridian, defined as the angular displacement between the sun current position and its position at solar noon. This angle is determined by the difference in hours between the given solar time and noon, multiplied by the Earth's angular velocity of 15° per hour. Since the Earth completes a full rotation of 360° in approximately 24 hours, its angular velocity is 15°/h.

The solar declination is the angle formed between the Earth's equatorial plane and the imaginary line that connects the centre of the Earth to the centre of the sun. This angular variation results from the inclination of the Earth's rotational axis relative to its orbital plane around the sun. Throughout the year, the declination varies between +23.45° and -23.45°. In the northern hemisphere, the maximum solar declination occurs at the summer solstice (+23.45°) and the minimum occurs at the winter solstice (-23.45°). The declination is null at both equinoxes.

The solar azimuth angle is the angle between the horizontal projection of the sun's rays and the true south direction, as illustrated in Figure 1. This angle is considered positive when westward and negative when eastward. The solar azimuth angle is calculated using the equations 6 and 7 [11].

$$\cos Az_{sl} = \frac{\sin Alt_{sl} \cdot \sin Lat - \sin \delta_{solar}}{\cos Alt_{sl} \cdot \cos Lat} \quad (6)$$

$$Az_{sl} = \begin{cases} 1 \cdot \arccos(\cos Az_{sl}), & h_{ang} \geq 0 \\ -1 \cdot \arccos(\cos Az_{sl}), & h_{ang} < 0 \end{cases} \quad (7)$$

where:

- Az_{sl} – solar azimuth [°];
- h_{ang} – solar hour angle [°];
- Alt_{sl} – solar altitude [°];
- Lat – latitude [°];
- δ_{solar} – solar declination [°].

The following step is the calculation of the sun position in relation to the surface in analysis. This is achieved from the altitude angle and azimuth angle, that characterize the direction of sun's rays, as well as the orientation and inclination of the surface, that characterize the surface direction, resulting in the incident angle, as show in Figure 2. The calculation of the solar rays' incident angle on the surface in analysis is shown in equation 8 [7].

$$\cos \theta = \cos Alt_{sl} \cdot \cos(Az_{sl} - Az_{sp}) \cdot \sin Incl_{sp} + \sin Alt_{sl} \cdot \cos Incl_{sp} \quad (8)$$

where:

- θ – incident angle [°];
- Alt_{sl} – solar altitude [°];
- AZ_{sl} – solar azimuth [°];
- AZ_{sp} – surface azimuth [°];
- $Incl_{sp}$ – surface tilt [°].

Figure 2. Incident angle of sun's rays on a surface

The solar irradiance is the solar radiant flux received by a surface per unit area. The total irradiance can be decomposed into three components: direct, diffuse and reflected. Direct irradiance refers to solar radiation that crosses the atmosphere and reaches the surface without suffering any dispersion in its trajectory, presenting rays parallel to the sun direction. On the other hand, diffuse irradiance results from the scattering of solar radiation caused by gases, particles and molecules present in the atmosphere. This scattering causes the rays to fall on the surface randomly, in various directions. Reflected irradiance corresponds to solar radiation that hits surrounding surfaces and is subsequently reflected towards the surface under analysis. The total solar irradiance is obtained by summing these three components, as expressed in equation 9.

$$I_T = I_D + I_{ds} + I_{dg} \quad (9)$$

where:

- I_T – total irradiance [W/m²];
- I_D – direct irradiance [W/m²];
- I_{ds} – diffuse irradiance [W/m²];
- I_{dg} – reflected irradiance [W/m²].

Direct normal irradiance, I_{DN} , is the incident solar radiation per unit area on a surface oriented perpendicularly to the direction of the sun's rays. According to the ASHRAE Handbook [7], I_{DN} is determined using equation 10:

$$I_{DN} = A_{sl} \cdot e^{\frac{-B}{\sin Alt_{sl}}} \quad (10)$$

where:

- I_{DN} – direct normal irradiance [W/m^2]
- A_{sl} – apparent solar irradiation [W/m^2]
- B – atmospheric extinction coefficient [-]
- Alt_{sl} – angle of solar altitude [$^\circ$]

The direct irradiance incident on a surface that is not perpendicular to the sun's rays is determined using equation 11 [7]. For this calculation, the irradiance will be considered negligible if the angle of incidence, defined as the angle between the surface normal and the direction of the sun's rays, exceeds 90° or is less than -90° . This condition ensures that irradiance is only calculated for valid incident angles, i.e. for situations where the surface is effectively exposed to direct solar radiation.

$$I_D = \begin{cases} I_{DN} \cdot \cos \theta, & \cos \theta > 0 \\ 0, & \cos \theta \leq 0 \end{cases} \quad (11)$$

where:

- I_D – direct irradiance [W/m^2];
- I_{DN} – direct normal irradiance [W/m^2];
- θ – incident angle [$^\circ$].

The diffuse irradiance, I_{ds} , is determined by applying equation 12 [7], which models the distribution of diffuse solar radiation as a function of various atmospheric and geographic parameters.

$$I_{ds} = \begin{cases} C \cdot Y \cdot I_{DN}, & Incl_{sp} = 90^\circ \\ C \cdot I_{DN} \cdot \frac{1 + \cos Incl_{sp}}{2}, & Incl_{sp} \neq 90^\circ \end{cases} \quad (12)$$

where:

- I_{ds} – diffuse irradiance [W/m^2];
- C – sky diffuse factor [-];
- Y – ratio of vertical/horizontal sky diffuse;
- I_{DN} – direct normal irradiance [W/m^2];
- $Incl_{sp}$ – surface tilt [$^\circ$];

The sky diffuse factor, C , is a tabulated value and can be found in ASHRAE Handbook (1997) [7]. The calculation of vertical/horizontal sky diffusion ratio is detailed in the ASHRAE Handbook [7]. The irradiance reflected by the ground and surrounding surfaces, I_{dg} , is calculated using equation 13 [7].

$$I_{dg} = I_{DN} \cdot (C + \sin Alt_{sl}) \cdot \rho_g \left(\frac{1 - \cos Incl_{sp}}{2} \right) \quad (13)$$

where:

- I_{dg} – reflected irradiance [W/m^2];
- I_{DN} – direct normal irradiance [W/m^2];

- C – sky diffuse factor [-];
 Alt_{sl} – solar altitude [°];
 ρ_g – ground reflectance [-];
 Incl_{sp} – surface tilt [°].

As previously presented, the sol-air temperature is used to estimate the heat gains on external wall and roof, and it considers the effects of outdoor air temperature and incident solar radiation, being calculated using equation 14 [7],

$$t_{sol} = t_{ext} + \frac{\alpha I_T}{h_0} - \varepsilon \frac{\Delta R}{h_0} \quad (14)$$

where:

- t_{sol} – sol-air temperature [°C];
 t_{out} – outdoor temperature [°C];
 α – absorptivity of surface for solar radiation [-];
 I_T – solar total irradiance [W/m²];
 h₀ – coefficient of heat transfer by convection at outer surface [W/m²K];
 ε – hemispherical emittance of surface [-];
 ΔR – difference between long-wave radiation incident on surface from sky and surroundings and radiation emitted by blackbody at outdoor air temperature [W/m²].

According to ASHRAE Handbook [7], the absorptivity value α is defined to 0.45 for light surfaces and 0.90 for dark surfaces or when no other information is available. For the convection coefficient at the outer surface, h₀, is considered a value of 17 W/(m²K), while it is assumed that hemispheric emittance, ε, is 1. The difference between the reflected radiation that falls on the surface and the radiation emitted by the black body, ΔR, is 63 W/m² on the horizontal surfaces and null (0 W/m²) for the vertical surfaces.

The solar heat gain factor, SHGF, is defined as the fraction of the total irradiance, I_T, that is transmitted directly into the interior of space, I_{trans}, or absorbed by the glass, I_{abs}. After the irradiance is absorbed by the glass, only a fraction, N_i, is transmitted into the space. This factor is used in the calculation of the heat gain from radiation transmitted through the windows and is determined using equation 15 [7].

$$SHGF = I_{trans} + N_i \cdot I_{abs} \quad (15)$$

where:

- SHGF – solar heat gain factor [W/m²];
 I_{trans} – transmitted irradiance [W/m²];
 N_i – inward heat transfer fraction [-];
 I_{abs} – absorbed irradiance [W/m²]

The fraction of the heat absorbed towards the space interior, N_i, is directly influenced by the type of glass used. According to ASHRAE Handbook [7], when no data is available, it can be

applied the reference glass value of 0.267 [7]. The irradiance transmitted and absorbed by the glass is determined using equations 16 and 17 [7], respectively. The thermal transmission coefficients, t_j , and thermal absorption coefficients, a_j , are parameters defined according to the type of glass, that can be found in the ASHRAE Handbook [7].

$$I_{trans} = I_D \sum_{j=0}^5 (t_j \cdot \cos^j \theta) + 2 \cdot I_d \sum_{j=0}^5 \left(\frac{t_j}{j+2} \right) \quad (16)$$

$$I_{abs} = I_D \sum_{j=0}^5 (a_j \cdot \cos^j \theta) + 2 \cdot I_d \cdot \sum_{j=0}^5 \left(\frac{a_j}{j+2} \right) \quad (17)$$

where:

- I_{trans} – transmitted irradiance [W/m^2];
- I_{abs} – absorbed irradiance [W/m^2];
- I_D – direct irradiance [W/m^2];
- I_d – sum of diffuse and reflected irradiance [W/m^2];
- t_j – glass transmission coefficients[-];
- a_j – glass absorption coefficients[-];
- θ – incident angle [$^\circ$]

3.2. COMPUTATIONAL MODELLING

The solar radiation model was implemented in a computational program developed in Python, allowing for the integration of the proposed equation across various scenarios. Python is an interpreted, object-oriented and high-level programming language with dynamic semantics. Its simplicity, ease to learn syntax emphasizes readability and, consequently, reduces program maintenance costs. Furthermore, Python supports modules and packages, which encourages program modularity and code reuse [12].

The data used for modelling solar radiation follows the previously presented methodology. The solar radiation calculation algorithm requires input data regarding three key aspects: Date & time; Location and Surfaces, as shown in Figure 3. From the date and time, parameters such as the hour, day since the start of the year and month can be obtained. The month is used to retrieve values for apparent solar irradiation, A_{sl} , atmospheric extinction coefficient, B , sky diffuse factor, C , and solar declination, δ_{solar} , by searching the tables available in ASHRAE Handbook [7]. The location data includes latitude, longitude and time zone, while surface data determine orientation and tilt.

Figure 3. Necessary data for solar radiation calculation

The developed computational model can be used by an user or an application, being necessary to provide the follow input arguments: date and time as datetime object; the latitude, longitude, time zone and surface tilt as a numerical data type (latitude, longitude and surface tilt must be in degrees); the surfaces orientation defined as strings indicating the cardinal directions (ex.: N, S, E, NE, etc...). Then, it is converted to corresponding orientation angle in degrees with a function as shown in Figure 4. This function employs a match-case structure to compare the input direction against predefined cardinal points, reading the argument of the function, and assign the corresponding angle (*orient_deg* variable), where south is 0°, east is -90° and west is 90°. If the input does not match any predefined direction, the function defaults to an angle equivalent to the south orientation (line 58-59), as this represents the worst-case scenario for locations in northern hemisphere.

```

24 def convert_orient_str_deg(orient_str: str):
25     match orient_str:
26         case "N":
27             orient_deg = -180
28 >
29 >
30 >
31 >
32 >
33 >
34         case "E":
35             orient_deg = -90
36 >
37 >
38 >
39 >
40 >
41 >
42         case "S":
43             orient_deg = 0
44 >
45 >
46 >
47 >
48 >
49 >
50         case "O":
51             orient_deg = 90
52 >
53 >
54 >
55 >
56 >
57 >
58         case _:
59             orient_deg = 0
60     return orient_deg

```

Figure 4. Function to convert orientation as a string to degrees in Python

The developed computational model implements the equations detailed in section 3, through dedicated programming functions. For instance, Figure 5 presents the function that computes the solar altitude based on equation 5. This function receives latitude, solar declination and the solar hour angle as input parameters and returns the value of solar altitude in radians. Non-calculated values angles, such as latitude or declination, are converted to radians. The solar hour angle is determined using a specific function, that returns an angle in radians, avoiding the need to convert it into radians later. The native Math library is required to compute trigonometric functions. After computing the sine of solar altitude, the angle of solar altitude is obtained using the inverse sine (*asin* – line 14) function, ensuring that the output remains in radians. A similar methodology was applied to implement all equations within the module.

```

3- def calc_solar_altitude(latitude, declinacao_solar, solar_hour_angle):
4   # Calculates the solar altitude [sl_alt], in radians, based on latitude, solar declination and solar hour angle,
5   # Latitude - In degrees
6   # Solar declination - In degrees
7   # Solar hour angle - In radians (calculated from the "calc_solar_hour_angle" function)
8
9   latitude_rad = math.radians(latitude)
10  declinacao_solar_rad = math.radians(declinacao_solar)
11
12  sen_sl_alt = (math.cos(latitude_rad) * math.cos(declinacao_solar_rad) * math.cos(solar_hour_angle)
13              + math.sin(latitude_rad) * math.sin(declinacao_solar_rad))
14  sl_alt = math.asin(sen_sl_alt)
15
16  return sl_alt

```

Figure 5. Function to calculate solar altitude in Python

After developing the functions necessary to compute all equations, it is created a function that implement the main algorithm and all functions that compute the individual functions. For example, Figure 6 illustrates the function that encases all functions needed to compute the solar heat gain factor, that will be used to estimate the heat gains on windows. The application of modular programming makes to code more structured, readable, reusable and easier to maintain and allows that different programs or users can use only specific functions in specific applications.

```

1- def calc_solar_heat_gain_factor_all(data_hora, longitude, TZN, latitude, orient_str, sf_incl, rho_g=0.2):
2   (...)
3
4   solar_time = calc_solar_time(hour, longitude, TZN, ET)
5
6   ang_hora_solar = calc_ang_hora_solar(solar_time)
7   sl_alt = calc_solar_altitude(latitude, declinacao_solar, ang_hora_solar)
8   sl_az = calc_solar_azimuth(latitude, declinacao_solar, sl_alt, ang_hora_solar)
9   sl_sf_incid_ang = calc_solar_surface_incident_angle(sl_alt, sl_az, sf_orient, sf_incl)
10
11  I_DN = calc_EDN(A, B, sl_alt)
12  I_D = calc_ED(I_DN, sl_sf_incid_ang)
13  I_ds = calc_E_ds(C, sl_sf_incid_ang, I_DN, sf_incl)
14  I_dg = calc_E_dg(C, I_DN, sl_alt, rho_g, sf_incl)
15
16  SHGF = solar_heat_gain(sl_sf_incid_ang, I_D, I_ds + I_dg)
17
18  return SHGF

```

Figure 6. Set of functions to calculate solar heat gain factor

In opposite to the solar heat gain factor, the sol-air temperature is computed from the data of the total solar irradiance and the outdoor air temperature. This would require introducing weather data into the solar radiation module, which falls beyond the scope of this module and this paper. Instead, a function is developed to estimate the total solar irradiance by implementing the corresponding equations in the code, as presented in Figure 6. The Figure 7 illustrates the algorithm used to estimate both the total solar irradiance and the solar heat gain factor, indicating also the required data for each equation/function.

Figure 7. Sequence of total solar irradiance and solar heat gain factor calculation

This module can be imported by users to estimate solar radiation via the command line. However, it is intended to include this module in applications, such as those for calculating the thermal load in buildings, as shown in Agostinho et al., (2024) [9].

4. VALIDATION

The computational module developed to estimate solar radiation incident on a surface was validated carrying out simulation tests considering the solar radiation on four surfaces, each one oriented towards the main cardinal directions. In these tests, the model computed solar radiation over an entire year, estimating the maximum values achieved in each month, for each surface. Furthermore, the developed model calculated the hourly radiation for the design day, defined as the day when thermal loads for a given space are at their peak. The results were compared with those obtained using the commercial program, Hourly Analysis Program (HAP) [13] version 4.8. Additionally, after validation, the solar radiation model was further tested and evaluated for multiple locations.

The HAP is a program developed by Carrier and it is widely used for the design Heating, Ventilation and Air Conditioning (HVAC) systems. This program allows the determination of thermal loads in a building and estimate the energy consumed. Additionally, it calculates the solar radiation incident on the building surfaces and incorporates this information into thermal load calculations, providing reports with detailed data. This allows the solar radiation results estimated by this commercial program to be used to validate the developed computational model.

The validation tests were performed considering a building located in Lisbon, with latitude 38,8 °N, longitude 9.1 °W and in the time zone of Greenwich Mean Time (GMT+0).

After defining the building location and considering that the vertical surfaces were oriented towards the north, east, south and west directions, respectively, the total solar irradiance was calculated using both the developed module and the HAP, for the design day of the month, throughout the year. Figure 8 shows the maximum solar irradiance in each month calculated by the developed model, in Python, and by HAP.

Figure 8. Monthly maximum total solar irradiance for 12 months to a) North, b) West, c) South and d) East

Analysing the Figure 8, it is observed that the surface towards to the north orientation reaches the maximum irradiance of 219 W/m^2 in June; For surfaces facing east and west, the peak irradiance of 812 W/m^2 occurs in April; and in the south-facing surface, the maximum irradiance of 913 W/m^2 occurs in January. The deviation between the Python module and HAP is less than 0.1%. It should be noted that the annual irradiance profile for the south-facing orientation exhibits an opposite trend compared to other orientations, with a maximum in January and a minimum in June. This behaviour is mainly attributed to the solar altitude angle, which is lower in January and higher in June, due to the variation in the solar declination angle, as computed by the equation 5. Consequently, this results in a smaller incidence angle of solar radiation in January and a greater angle in June, in accordance with equation 8.

When comparing the maximum solar irradiance for all month, it is also essential to evaluate the irradiance absorbed by surfaces at each hour of a given day, particularly on the day when maximum irradiance occurs. Analysing the Figure 8, it is possible to observe that the maximum irradiance occurs in different months depending on the orientation.

To utilise this module for the computation of thermal loads in buildings, the python module is applied to the day on which the maximum thermal load for a given space is observed. For this

purpose, a test was conducted using a model with four walls, each with a window, oriented towards north, west, south and east. The characteristics of the walls and windows are detailed in Table 1. These parameters were introduced in HAP to estimate the thermal loads in the building along the year. The results indicate that the maximum thermal load in the space occurs in September at 3 p.m. This analysis enables the characterisation of combined effect of solar irradiance from all orientations on thermal loads of building, although there is some effect due to variation of outdoor temperature.

Type	Orientation	Area [m ²]	U	α (wall) /SC (window)
Wall	North, West, South, East	50	0.24	0.45
Window	North, West, South, East	10	1.6	0.61

Table 1. Characteristics of wall and windows for thermal loads analysis

The analysis of the total irradiance evolution on the day of the highest thermal load, which occurred in September, was estimated using Python program and with the HAP. The results are presented in Figure 9.

Considering the surfaces orientation and the geographic location in the northern hemisphere, the irradiance observed from sunrise until 12.p.m on west-facing surface and from 12 p.m. until sunset in east orientation is the same as that observed in north orientation, in those hours. This indicates that, during these hours, irradiance is predominantly diffuse. Outside these periods, the irradiance is primarily direct. The irradiance recorded on the south-facing surface from sunrise to sunset results from a combination of direct and diffuse components.

Analysing the obtained data, it is observed that in the north orientation, the maximum irradiance was recorded at 12 p.m., reaching 117.9 W/m² with a maximum deviation of 0.2%, occurring at 7 a.m., corresponding to the first hour of solar radiation incidence. On the west-facing surface, the maximum irradiance was obtained at 4 p.m., with a value of 744.7 W/m², while the highest deviation of 4.9% occurred at 12 p.m., corresponding to the first hour that direct irradiance was obtained. The maximum irradiance in the south-facing orientation was also observed at 12 p.m., with a value of 734.5 W/m², and the maximum deviation of 0.1% occurred at 5 p.m., corresponding to the last hour of solar radiation. Finally, the maximum irradiance in the east-facing surface was reached at 8 a.m., with a value of 747.8 W/m², and the highest deviation of 0.3% occurred at 12 p.m., which corresponds to the last hour that direct irradiance was obtained.

Overall, it is observed that, in all orientations, the highest deviations occurred during periods of greater variation in solar radiation. Nevertheless, these deviations remain relatively low, indicating a strong agreement in the irradiance calculations throughout the day.

Figure 9. Hourly total solar irradiance for maximum thermal load day to a) North, b) West, c) South and d) East

In order to validate the radiation model at different locations, the same tests were carried out in four different cities: Lisbon, Portugal; Paris, France; Stockholm, Sweden and Houston, Texas, U.S. As illustrated in Figure 3, solar radiation is influenced by the latitude, longitude and time zone of a given location. Table 2 presents the latitude, longitude and corresponding time zone of each city, adopting the convention that westward longitudes are positive, while eastward longitudes are negative.

City, Country	Latitude	Longitude	Time zone
Lisbon, Portugal	38.8 °N	9.1 °W	GMT 0
Paris, France	48.5 °N	2.1 °E	GMT -1
Stockholm, Sweden	59.4 °N	18.0 °E	GMT -1
Houston, Texas, U.S.	30.0 °N	95.4 °W	GMT 6

Table 2. Geographical data and time zone data of Lisbon, Paris, Stockholm and Houston.

Figure 10a shows the hourly solar irradiance as a function of solar time for the day with the highest thermal load, considering a south-facing orientation. Figure 10b shows the same relationship for a day in December. In the developed model, the use of solar time eliminates the influence of equation 4, which accounts for the calculation of solar time, thereby ensuring

that solar irradiance is independent of local longitude and time zone. Consequently, variations in location affect only the latitude.

Figure 10. Total solar irradiance for south orientation for various locations in a) September and b) December as a function of solar time

The first notable aspect in Figure 10a is that the duration of solar exposure is identical for all locations. This occurs because in September is the equinox, during which day and night have equal duration regardless of geographical position. The irradiance in September (Figure 10a) is higher at locations with greater latitude. This is due to the fact that higher latitude correspond to lower solar altitude (equation 5), which results in a lower incidence angle (equation 8). As demonstrated in equation 11, a lower incidence angle leads to higher direct irradiance.

Analysing Figure 10b, the duration of solar exposure is greater for locations at lower latitudes. In this case, the graph represents the winter solstice. The irradiance in December (Figure 10b) is higher for locations with lower latitude. This occurs because, in equation 5, the solar declination is negative, whereas it was zero in September. Consequently, in December, the reduction in solar altitude is less noticeable for location with lower latitude. In other words, locations at higher latitudes experience a lower altitude angle. From equation 10, it follows that direct normal irradiance decreases as the solar altitude angle decreases.

After analysing solar radiation as a function of solar time, which depends solely on latitude, it is also necessary to evaluate solar radiation based on local time. This means that equation 4 is considered. This equation introduces the effect of local longitude and time zone of each location. Figure 11 shows the hourly irradiance as function of local time for September (Figure 11a) and December (Figure 11b). The noticeable difference compared to Figure 10 is a time shift in the irradiance profile throughout the day. This results from the $l_{sr}-l_{local}$ term in equation 4, indicating that irradiance is influenced by displacement between the local longitude and the standard meridian longitude, rather than by longitude alone. However, the maximum irradiance remains approximately the same.

Figure 11. Total solar irradiance for south orientation for various locations in a) September and b) December as a function of local time

5. CONCLUSIONS

The presented study aimed to develop a computational model for incident solar radiation and evaluate its application in the calculation of thermal loads in buildings. This was achieved through the implementation of equations that compute solar time, solar position angles and estimate the solar radiation on an oriented surface, hourly, throughout the year. For radiation on opaque elements such as walls and roofs, the effect of solar radiation is considered through sol-air temperature. In the case of radiation on windows, the impact of solar radiation was considered through solar heat gain factor.

These calculations were developed as a module in Python, where each equation was implemented as an individual function. The model relies on input data such as the building's geographical location, date and time, and the characteristics of the surfaces such as orientation and tilt. This module can operate as a standalone tool for direct solar radiation calculations. On the other hand, this is intended to be used on thermal load calculation program such as presented in Agostinho et al., (2024) [9].

The validation process involved comparing the results obtained with those generated by a commercial reference program, HAP. For the maximum monthly irradiance calculated over a year in Lisbon, the highest observed deviation was below 0,1%. The maximum irradiance occurred in January for south-facing surfaces, in April for east and west-facing surfaces, and in June for north-facing surfaces. The maximum thermal load of the space was considered to account for the contribution of irradiance from all orientations. The observed deviations remained below 5%, demonstrating the composition of direct and diffuse irradiance in the total incident solar irradiance.

Subsequently, the effect of location on solar irradiance was evaluated by considering both solar time and local time. When using solar time, irradiance was found to depend solely on the latitude, influencing both the peak irradiance and the duration of solar exposure depending on the specific time of year. In contrast, considering local time includes also the effect of longitude and time zone, introducing a time shift in the irradiance profile throughout the day

compared to the irradiance profile based on solar time.

In summary, the presented paper enables the modelling of solar radiation, with results demonstrating a strong correlation with those obtained from other software tools.

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